

IPAD-MD

Deliverable 3.2 (WP3)

Summary report on the alignment of the INFRAFRONTIER scientific agenda with national, European and international research policies

Reported by:

Ass. Prof. Dr. Radislav Sedlacek, Dr. Asrar Ali Khan and Dr. Michael Raess

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1. Introduction

IPAD-MD, a project funded under the European Union Horizon 2020 program, addresses global cooperation and coordination between the pan-European INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure and complementary research infrastructures in America, Asia and Australia, contributing to the global effort of the IMPC, and with complementary research infrastructures and users in Africa.

It has a particular focus on **involving the key stakeholders** (user communities such as the rare diseases community, other patient organisations, industry, funders and policy makers) in shaping the resources and services provided by INFRAFRONTIER and the IMPC.

IPAD-MD organised a series of workshops that brought together representatives of the INFRAFRONTIER and IMPC research infrastructures and of their key stakeholders to achieve three major objectives:

1. **Strengthen the coordination** between the global research infrastructures in the field of the systemic phenotyping, archiving and distribution of mouse disease models. A particular emphasis of IPAD-MD was to improve global access to the common resources created by INFRAFRONTIER and the IMPC and to align the scientific strategy with international research agendas.
2. **Engage key international stakeholders** to improve the resources and services offered by INFRAFRONTIER and established in the context of the IMPC. Furthermore, IPAD-MD will involve funders and program agencies in the discussions about the future of the resources and services developed in INFRAFRONTIER and the IMPC.

3. **Coordinate globally the development** of innovative technology solutions for the improvement of the resources and services provided by INFRAFRONTIER and the IMPC.

Within the IPAD-MD project, **the WP3 - Engagement with Funders & Policy** is aiming at:

1. Providing an overview of the strategic research agendas and national, European and global research policies relevant to IPAD-MD
2. Providing thematic input to the IPAD-MD workshops
3. Ensuring the alignment of the scientific agendas of INFRAFRONTIER and the IMPC with national, European and international research agendas.

In this report we summarise the activities within the IPAD-MD project that allowed us to shape INFRAFRONTIER's scientific strategy in a way that aligns with the needs of our key user communities and with the research agendas of key science policy stakeholders on the national, European and international level.

This report also incorporates the recommendations of **D3.1 - Survey on European and International Research Agendas**.

2. Summary of alignment activities

2.1 Focal Areas

D3.2 identified five focal areas, where the INFRAFRONTIER and IMPC partners saw specific potential for scientific activities in the coming years: Metabolism, rare diseases, ageing and neurodegenerative diseases, and inflammation / immunology.

Fig. 1: Results from the survey on research priorities carried out for D3.1: the five most selected areas in which INFRAFRONTIER and the IMPC consortia should focus on.

2.2 Metabolism / Diabetes

Metabolic diseases and diabetes were addressed in presentations and posters at the large INFRAFRONTIER stakeholder events although these conditions were not specifically targeted as thematic focus areas at the events. Metabolic diseases and diabetes are scientific research priorities for some of the INFRAFRONTIER partners, such as the Helmholtz Center Munich in Germany, Czech Centre for Phenogenomics, and the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona in Spain, and as recommended in D3.1, we mainly leveraged these local connections to receive feedback about our resources for this research field.

Of the five IMI initiatives targeting diabetes, IMIDIA and Summit are already concluded. The three currently running IMI projects DIRECT, Rhapsody and INNODIA could be targeted in future INFRAFRONTIER stakeholder events.

2.3 Rare Diseases

Aligning the INFRAFRONTIER and IMPC resources to the requirements of the rare diseases research community and to rare diseases programmes on the national and European level was one of the major areas of activities of INFRAFRONTIER since the publication of D3.1.

Rare diseases were thematic focus areas of two large INFRAFRONTIER/IMPC stakeholder events, the **INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Stakeholder Meeting 2017** in Athens and the **INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Stakeholder Meeting 2018** in Munich (see also *Table 1*).

In 2019, INFRAFRONTIER created a dedicated landing page for rare diseases researchers. This page provides quick access to the resources and services that INFRAFRONTIER provides for this research field: a list of RD relevant mouse strains in the EMMA archive, a list of publications about EMMA strains related diseases, and information about INFRAFRONTIER events that target rare diseases.

INFRAFRONTIER & Rare Diseases

INFRAFRONTIER and Rare Diseases

Mouse Models for Rare Disease Research

According to the [EU](#), a rare disease is defined as a disease afflicting fewer than one in 2000 individuals. It is estimated that 30 million people in Europe suffer from a rare disease. There are currently about 7000 rare diseases known with more being discovered continually ([ref](#)). The field of rare diseases suffers from a deficit of medical and scientific knowledge. They are also referred to "orphan diseases" having been orphaned by the pharmaceutical industry because of small patient populations and consequently a smaller drug market. Scientifically, these diseases reside in the 'unchartered space' of biomedical research with their treatment marred by a dearth of medical and biochemical knowledge. Apart from being a huge emotional and financial burden to patients and their families, treatment of such rare diseases also significantly impacts public health care services and is plagued by several hidden costs. [Angelis et al \(2015\)](#).

- The INFRAFRONTIER Stakeholder Meeting 2018 on rare disease research and gene therapy applications with animal models. Find more information on the conference [here](#) >.
- INFRAFRONTIER members will be present at the [RE\(ACT\) Conferece](#) in Toronto.

EMMA Strains and Rare Diseases

Find a list of rare diseases that are related to EMMA mouse strains [here](#) >.

EMMA Publications and Rare Diseases

Find all publications about EMMA strains that are related to rare diseases [here](#) >.

INFRAFRONTIER and Rare Disease Conferences

Fig. 2: Screenshot of the rare diseases landing page on the INFRAFRONTIER website <https://www.infrafrontier.eu/infrafrontier-and-rare-diseases>.

Since January 2019 INFRAFRONTIER is a partner in the EC funded programme *European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases (EJP-RD)*, which allows direct

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interaction with the different national funding bodies involved in setting up this Joint Programme, as well as with EURORDIS as the European umbrella patient organisation for rare diseases.

With those activities the main recommendations of the D3.1 report (landing page, synergies with the E-Rare Programme, now EJP-RD, and EURORDIS) were all met.

2.4 Ageing

The topic of ageing and the interactions with ageing research initiatives as recommended in the D3.1 report was well represented at the IPAD-MD stakeholder events. At the **INFRAFRONTIER Industry & Innovation Workshop, in Munich** in June 2016 the COST action MouseAge was presented, and ageing research in general was a thematic focus of the **INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Conference 2019** in Helsinki, with several different presentations on that topic.

The IMPC has meanwhile established a dedicated **late-adult pipeline** to identify late onset phenotypes that manifest in mice that are older than 1 year of age. Depending on the strategy of the different participating centres, either one mouse cohort is running through the standard phenotyping pipeline at young and at older age, or two matched cohorts are run through the early-onset and late-onset pipelines respectively.

Fig. 3: Scheme of the IMPC phenotyping pipelines, the late adult pipeline starts at an age of 49 to 70 weeks, depending on the specific strategies of the participating centres.

2.5 Neurodegenerative Diseases and Inflammation / Immunology

The disease areas of the neurodegenerative diseases and inflammation / immunology were not specifically targeted in the large IPAD-MD stakeholder events, were however partly covered in other thematic focus areas such as ageing.

2.6 Summary of scientific areas and stakeholders targeted at the IPAD-MD stakeholder events

Table 1 provides a summary of the different IPAD-MD stakeholder events and the thematic areas and key stakeholders that were targeted.

Table 1: Overview of the different priority areas targeted in the large IPAD-MD stakeholder engagement events.

Event	Date	Stakeholders targeted
IPAD-MD Kick-Off Meeting, Munich	July 2015	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INFRAFRONTIER and IMPC • International Human Epigenome Consortium (IHEC) • IMI NEWSMED • Outreach to Africa: University of Cape Town
INFRAFRONTIER Industry & Innovation Workshop, Munich	June 2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INFRAFRONTIER and IMPC • Ageing Community: COST Action MouseAge • EATRIS • Industry and SME stakeholders: • Actual Analytics • Ayoxxa Biosystems • Biomedcode • Charles River • Cryoport • Data Science International • GSK – Open Targets • InnoSer Laboratories BV • Janssen R&D • Merck (Sigma Aldrich)

Event	Date	Stakeholders targeted
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Polygene • Tecniplast • TSE Systems
<p>INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Stakeholder Meeting 2017, Athens</p>	<p>Nov 2017</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INFRAFRONTIER and IMPC • Research focus: Personalised Medicine and Rare Diseases • Genomics England • JAX Center for Precision Genetics • JAX Rare and Orphan Disease Center • EurOPDX • RD-Connect • ICPeMed • IRDiRC • European Medicines Agency (EMA) • European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations (EFPIA)
<p>INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Stakeholder Meeting 2018, Munich</p>	<p>Dec 2018</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INFRAFRONTIER and IMPC • Research focus: Rare Diseases • Undiagnosed Disease Network • Monarch Initiative • European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases • Genomics England • Canadian Rare Disease Models and Mechanisms Network (RDMM) • Research focus: Gene Therapy • GENETHON • SR-TIGET • NIH Somatic Cell Genome Editing Program

Event	Date	Stakeholders targeted
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ARRIGE - Association for Responsible Research and Innovation in Genome Editing • ESFRI
INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Conference 2019, Helsinki	Jun 2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INFRAFRONTIER and IMPC • Research focus: Genetic Variation • Scandinavian Disease Heritage Centers: FinnGen, FarGen • Research focus: Ageing • German Center for Neurodegenerative Diseases • FET-Flagship LIFETIME • EurOPDX • Euro-Biolmaging

3. Alignment with recent research policy initiatives

3.1 European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

The European Commission put forward the strategy for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) as a part of its Digital Single Market Strategy. The objective of the EOSC is to give the Union a global lead in research data management and ensure that European scientists reap the full benefits of data-driven science, by offering *'1.7 million European researchers and 70 million professionals in science and technology a virtual environment with free at the point of use, open and seamless services for storage, management, analysis and re-use of research data, across borders and scientific disciplines'*¹.

In March 2019, the Horizon 2020 funded **EOSC-Life project**² started with the participation of INFRAFRONTIER. In EOSC-Life the 13 biological and medical research infrastructures in Europe join forces to create an open, collaborative digital space for life science in the European Open Science Cloud. They will do this by publishing their data as FAIR data resources, linking reusable tools and workflows to standardised computing services in national life-science clouds, connecting users across Europe to a single login authentication and resource authorisation system, and developing the data policies needed to preserve and

¹ COM(2016)178 final – EC Communication on the 'European Cloud Initiative

² <https://www.eosc-life.eu>

deepen the trust given by research participants and patients volunteering their data and samples.

INFRAFRONTIER GmbH is aligned with EOSC via the EOSC-Life project:

INFRAFRONTIER GmbH co-leads WP8 (International Impact, Innovation and Sustainability) and actively contributes to WP1 (Publishing FAIR RI data resources in EOSC), WP2 (Tools Collaboratory: Deployment of life-science data integration and analysis workflows in EOSC), WP3 (Demonstrators and Open Calls for User Projects) and WP5 (User management and access services). Moreover, together with IF partner EMBL-EBI, INFRAFRONTIER GmbH is addressing the topic of IMPC data sustainability within the context of EOSC-Life.

3.2 Horizon Europe Cancer mission

In 2019 the European Commission announced the missions that a number of missions will be included in Horizon Europe, the next framework programme, and these will specifically target global challenges. The target would be clearly measurable and need to be achievable with a portfolio of research and innovation measures.

Currently five missions have been identified, and among them is one health related **mission on cancer**. Cancer affects everyone regardless of age, gender or social status and represents a tremendous burden for patients, families, and societies at large. If no further action is taken, the number of people newly

diagnosed with cancer every year in Europe will increase from the current 3.5 million to more than 4.3 million by 2035³.

A mission in this area will help set common goals aiming to reverse these frightening trends in cancer. By joining efforts across Europe, more people would live without cancer, more cancer patients would be diagnosed earlier, would suffer less and have a better quality of life after treatment.

This cancer mission area has a mission board tasked with identifying one or more specific missions for implementation under Horizon Europe. The mission board consists of 15 experts, including the chair, and is supported by a mission secretariat and an assembly. They will have to propose concrete targets and timelines for each mission by the end of 2019.

In order to align INFRAFRONTIER activities with this newly announced cancer mission, cancer will be a thematic priority of the **INFRAFRONTIER Conference 2020** which will take place in Brussels in October 2020. Prof. Tomi Mäkelä, member of the Cancer Mission Board, will present about the Cancer Mission and be involved in cancer research policy discussions. In addition, a new INFRAFRONTIER cancer page is being generated that will help clinical researchers narrow down EMMA strains for cancer research. This page will have IMPC strains presented with phenotypic descriptions as well.

³ https://ec.europa.eu/info/horizon-europe-next-research-and-innovation-framework-programme/mission-area-cancer_en